
ACTIVITIES REPORT 2025

INFORMATICS
EUROPE

Informatics Europe 2025 Activities Report

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President's Executive Summary

Dear members, colleagues and friends,

In 2025, Informatics Europe (IE) continued to strengthen its role as a collective voice of the Informatics research and education community in Europe, advancing key priorities and supporting policy through coordinated actions and community engagement.

Guided by our [Strategic Focus Areas](#), we addressed both **timely issues and long-term challenges** shaping the discipline. This includes our continued contribution to **Informatics in Schools**, a strategic goal pursued since 2012, and the celebration of the **10th anniversary of the Minerva Informatics Equality Award**, marking a decade of sustained impact built on IE's pioneering effort to promote gender equality in Informatics Departments. This milestone was marked by the publication of a dedicated catalogue showcasing impactful practices to advance diversity and inclusion across Europe.

Our community initiatives continue to grow in reach and impact. The European Informatics Leaders Summit (**ECSS**) remains our flagship event, bringing together key stakeholders to turn shared challenges into collective progress. The **Best Dissertation Award** and the **SCHIER summer school** further consolidate their role in fostering excellence, leadership and capacity building. **New task forces** have advanced work on transversal Informatics **skills** across disciplines, the integration of **AI in Informatics Higher Education**, or the evolving needs in **cybersecurity** education. The launch of two **new Working Groups on Software Research** and **Early Career Researchers** further expands our impact in research and career development.

Key outcomes of these efforts are reflected in the [Outcomes Summary](#) of this report, including the annual update of the **IE Higher Education Data Portal** and the publication of six **reports** and four **policy recommendations**, broadly disseminated and discussed with relevant national and European stakeholders. These outputs support evidence-based decision-making and strengthen the positioning of Informatics in European discussions.

Membership growth continues to reinforce our network. In 2025, we welcomed **12 new member institutions**, bringing our total to 186 institutions across 33 countries and strengthening our capacity to represent the community with authority.

As outlined in the [Conclusion & Future Outlook](#) section, IE will continue to support the discipline and its members through strengthened **advocacy**, increased **visibility**, and strategic **resources** to navigate a rapidly evolving landscape.

I would like to thank all those who contribute to IE's mission in 2025 and encourage readers to share this report widely and engage in ongoing IE activities. Together, we continue to strengthen our community and its capacity to shape the future of Informatics.

Jean-Marc Jézéquel
President, Informatics Europe

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Introduction

In 2025, Informatics Europe continued to support and empower its members in advancing the quality, visibility, and societal impact of Informatics research and education across Europe, contributing to the further consolidation of the discipline and strengthening its position alongside more established fields.

Through shared knowledge, coordinated actions, and collective visibility, the association addressed common challenges and supported policymaking at institutional, national and European levels.

Informatics Europe is led by a Board of Directors composed of academic leaders from institutions across Europe, and supported by a dedicated office team that manages daily operations, membership and communications. Its Working Groups, open to IE members, play a central role by bringing together community expertise to bridge research, education and policy across key strategic areas of the discipline (see [Organisational Structure Annex](#)).

Strategic Focus Areas

This section highlights key initiatives and achievements during 2025, reflecting the collective work of Informatics Europe's working groups, Board, and community at large.

Descriptions have been intentionally kept concise to provide a comprehensive yet easy-to-read overview of the year's activities. Further details on each initiative are available via the links provided.

Education

The **Education Research Working Group (WG)**, chaired by **Jan Vahrenhold**, advanced several initiatives addressing emerging educational challenges and opportunities:

- Informatics in School: continued contribution to the **Informatics for All coalition**, represented by **Enrico Nardelli** and **Ángel Velázquez**, which produced two key outcomes in 2025: the *Response to the AI Literacy Framework developed by the European Commission and OECD*, and a *European Survey on Requirements for the Informatics School Curriculum and Informatics School Teachers' Education*.
- **SCHIER (Summer School on Informatics Education Research)** held its second edition at UCLouvain (Belgium), with **IBM Research Europe** as the main sponsor. Chaired by **Enrico Nardelli** and locally organised by **Kim Mens**, it gathered participants from 17 institutions across 10 countries, strengthening the European Informatics education research community.
- **EC's Expert Group on Informatics Education**, with IE represented by **Enrico Nardelli**, and contributions from **Michael E. Caspersen**, **Violetta Lonati** and **Keith Quille** from the WG.
- **Guidelines on Assessing Informatics Students (AI-centric approaches)**, a report developed by **Heri Ramampiaro** following the discussion during the ECSS 2024 session co-organised with National Informatics Associations (NIAs).
- **Academia–industry Collaboration in Higher Education**: building on ECSS 2024 [discussions](#), this effort focuses on bachelor's and master's theses, industrial doctorates, capstone projects and work-based learning to produce a best-practices report in 2026.
- **K-12 Education Research**, exploring collaboration opportunities and funding initiatives related to school-level Informatics education.

- **Data Science Education Standards & Recommendations:** continued collaboration with the Federation of European National Statistical Societies (FEnStat) and the European Association for Data Science (EuADS).
- **Informatics Skills as a Transversal Competence across Degrees**, a task force led by **Ernestina Menasalvas** and **Agustín Yagüe**, launched an analysis of Informatics competencies beyond Informatics degrees, to support curriculum alignment with the Digital Decade 2030 skills agenda.
- Two **task forces** were launched in 4Q2025, one on **AI in Informatics Higher Education**, led by **Oana Andrei** and **Maria Kallia**, and another one on **Quantum Computing Education**, led by **Elisabetta Di Nitto**.
- **Cybersecurity Education**, led by **Gert Jervan**, analysed labour-market needs and provision in Europe, identified the lack of EU-wide guidelines, and initiated outreach to launch a task force to define IE's role.
- Continued collaboration for the ACM annual conference on Innovation and Technology in Informatics Education (**ITICSE**). **Viola Lonati** continues to represent IE in its steering committee.

Research

- **Published the Informatics Research Evaluation 2025 Revised Report**, developed under the leadership of **Pekka Orponen** and **Manuel Carro** and supported by the representatives of IE's NIAs.
- **Open letter** addressing the **Critical Omission of Software Technology in the EIC Work Programme 2025**, broadly shared with the community and particularly discussed with the EC.
- **Policy Statement and Call to Action on Open Access Publishing** highlighted concerns about rising costs and inequities in Gold Open Access models and called for fairer, more sustainable alternatives.
- **Open Science & Open-Source Workshop** at **ECSS 2025**, chaired by **Lenuta Alboaie** and **Philippe Krief**, focused on the concrete implementation of Open Science at universities.
- **Professional Development Workshop for Early Career Researchers (ECR)** at **ECSS 2025**, chaired by **Dimka Karastoyanova**, centred on supporting professional growth through inter-generational collaboration.
- **Best Dissertation Award** (sponsored by **Springer**) recognised outstanding doctoral research in Informatics. The 2025 award was granted to **Andrea Cini** (Università della Svizzera italiana) for the dissertation "*Graph Deep Learning for Time Series Forecasting.*" Three runners-up and two finalists were also acknowledged and invited to contribute to the ECR Workshop during ECSS. The selection was carried out by an Award Committee composed of IE Board members, chaired by **Přemek Brada** and **Dimka Karastoyanova**.
- **Software Research WG**, chaired by **Tanja Vos**, launched to strengthen collaboration across software research communities, to position software research as a strategic priority in Europe, and to promote software as a core research output alongside publications and datasets.
- **Early Career Researchers WG**, chaired by **Dimka Karastoyanova**, launched to strengthen networking and collaboration across Europe, addressing career development challenges.

Diversity & Inclusion

The Diversity and Inclusion **WG**, led by **Simona Motogna**, continued advancing initiatives to promote gender balance and inclusive practices in Informatics:

- **ECSS 2025 Workshop: “Voices of Inclusion: Experiences and Initiatives”**, organised by **Simona Motogna, Oana Andrei** and **Lola Burgueño**, highlighted the value of shared experiences, mentorship and community-driven approaches to boost inclusion in Informatics academic settings.
- **Webinar “United for Impact: Women in Informatics”**, organised in March 2025 for International Women’s Day, bringing together organisational perspectives from across Europe.
- **10th Minerva Informatics Equality Award** was awarded to **the Department of Computer Science at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)** for the initiative *“From ADA to AI”*, recognising its 30+ years of sustained institutional impact in promoting gender balance in Informatics. The runner-up, **TalTech**, was recognised for its innovative, tech-driven *“Diversifying IT”* initiative. The Award Committee was chaired by **Sarah Jane Delany**.
- **Minerva Informatics Equality Award Catalogue**, published in October, provided a structured resource to guide institutions in designing and implementing diversity and inclusion strategies.
- **Representation in European events** included participation by **Simona Motogna** in the *Women in Digital Summit 2025* (Brussels), and by **Ana Belén Gil González** at ICODSIP 2025 panel *“The Missing Talent: Aligning Digital Skills with Industry Needs”* (Madrid).
- **EUGAIN Handbook of Intervention Methods “Actions for Gender Balance in Informatics Across Europe”**, published as a final outcome of COST Action **EUGAIN CA19122** - European Network for Gender Balance in Informatics, where IE was initiator and grant holder.
- Closure of the **Erasmus+ Inclusion4EU project**, where IE was the communication and dissemination partner. Outcomes include a European framework for inclusive software design (guidelines, checklists, patterns) and open educational resources for Informatics education.

Ethics

Led by **Covadonga Rodrigo** as chair of the **WG** and **Elisabetta Di Nitto** as Board member representative, IE continued exploring the integration of ethical considerations into Informatics education and research:

- **ECSS 2025 Session “Societal Impact of ICT and its interaction with human beings”**, chaired by **Covadonga Rodrigo**, featured WG contributions and a round table co-organised with ERCIM.
- **Ethics in Informatics Studies**, an analysis of existing WG members’ data, which led to three new initiatives, to be implemented and reviewed in 2026.
- Endorsement of the **DIGHUM Open Letter on Digital Technologies Regulation**, supporting calls for responsible governance of digital technologies.

Green ICT

Chaired by **Marco Aiello** until November and **Monica Vitali** thereafter, the Green ICT **WG** focused on:

- **ECSS 2025 Session on Green ICT** facilitated discussions on the environmental impact of computing infrastructures, software efficiency and the role of Informatics in enabling sustainable innovation.
- **COST Action proposal “Green ICT for the Future”** submitted in October 2025, contributing to the consolidation of a European research network in this area.
- Ongoing **European study on Green ICT practices**, coordinated by **Patricia Lago**, analysing practices in both research and industry.
- **White Paper on Green ICT**, under development, to provide guidance for institutions.

Data Gathering, Analysis & Reporting

Data gathering is mainly coordinated by the IE Office, while **Přemek Brada** and **Ana C. R. Paiva** chaired the Data Analysis & Reporting **WG**. Highlights in this area include:

- **Informatics Europe Higher Education Data Portal** updated with 2023/24 data and expanded to include Iceland (25 countries in total), bringing coverage to 25 countries and further strengthening its role as a key European resource for evidence-based decision-making.
- **Bachelor-level Informatics Education in Europe Report (2018/19–2022/23)**, analysing enrolment, graduation rates, gender distribution and institutional differences across 24 European countries.
- Joint report with ACM Europe on **European Informatics Retention and Graduation Rate Report**, based on IE Data Portal data, providing the first pan-European analysis of student progression and completion across 13 countries (2010–2023).

Community Empowerment and Growth

All IE activities aim to strengthen the European Informatics community and support its members from a strategic and institutional perspective. The following highlights those with a broader impact on community building and institutional development, with cross-cutting contributions across Informatics education, research and societal impact:

- **European Informatics Leaders Summit - ECSS 2025** (21st edition) took place in Rennes, France, chaired by **Jean-Marc Jézéquel** and hosted by IRISA – University of Rennes, as part of IRISA’s 50th anniversary celebration. As an established forum for exchange and coordination on strategic and managerial aspects of the discipline, ECSS 2025 attracted **130 participants**, representing over **90 institutions** across **26 European countries**.
- Beyond the above-mentioned workshops, organised by IE WGs, the program included the traditional **Leaders Workshop**, this year titled “*How to Cope with Changes in Informatics Departments?*”, co-chaired by **Ana C. R. Paiva** and **Jean-Marc Jézéquel**. The keynote session featured **Manuel Wimmer** on “*Integrating Quantum Technologies into European Informatics Departments*”. Co-organised with IE member NIAs, the Upskilling & Societal Engagement Workshop was chaired by **Heri Ramampiaro**.
- **Department Assessment Service** delivered to DISCo, University of Milano-Bicocca, coordinated by **Harald Gall**. Results were highly valued, with a follow-up planned for 2027.
- Contributions to **EU-funded projects and proposals**, including the conclusion of the **Inclusion4EU** Erasmus+ project and the submission of several COST and Erasmus+ proposals: **MINDtheGAP**, on how digitalisation, AI and new technologies reshape intergenerational knowledge transfer and mental health in technology-focused workplaces; **EMBRACE-IT**, aiming at empowering first-year female students to embrace IT courses; **EUGAME** - European Network for Game-Based Learning and Training Engineering; and the awarded **AIM-PRO: AI Literacy for Multidisciplinary Professional Readiness and Outreach**, an Erasmus+ project starting in February 2026, led by the University of L’Aquila.
- **Community Growth and Engagement**, led by IE office staff and strongly supported by **Kim Mens** and **Ana C. R. Paiva**. Ongoing outreach efforts contributed to further strengthening ties with existing members while welcoming **12 new institutions** in 2025:

Academic Members

- Faculty of Computer Science, University of Namur (BE)
- Department of Computer Science, Aalborg University (DK)
- Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería Informática (ETSII), Universidad de Sevilla (ES)
- Computer Science Department, University of Crete (GR)
- School of Informatics, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (GR)
- Department of Computer Science, University of Pisa (IT)
- Faculty of Mathematics and Informatics, Vilnius University (LT)
- Department of Informatics, University of Oslo (NO)
- Computer Science Department, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca (RO)
- Department of Computer Science and Media Technology, Linnaeus University (SE)

Associate Members

- Eclipse Foundation
- HNF - Heinz Nixdorf MuseumsForum GmbH

Growing to **186 institutions** across **33 countries** by the end of 2025, the expanded membership strengthens IE's ability to take decisive action and amplify our impact as a voice of authority in Europe.

Outcomes Summary

Key reports and resources based on the work of our working groups, strategic initiatives and community discussions in 2025 are listed in this section with direct hyperlinks:

Policy Recommendations

- [Endorsement of the DIGHUM Open Letter on Digital Technologies Regulation](#)
- [The Critical Omission of Software Technology in the EIC Work Programme 2025](#)
- [General Guidelines on How to Assess Informatics \(or Higher Education\) Students: AI-centric Approaches](#)
- [Policy Statement and Call to Action on Open Access Publishing](#)

Reports

- [The 2025 Revised Report on Informatics Research Evaluation](#)
- [A European Survey on Requirements for the Informatics School Curriculum and Informatics School Teachers' Education](#)
- [EUGAIN Handbook of Intervention Methods "Actions for Gender Balance in Informatics Across Europe"](#)
- [European Informatics Retention and Graduation Rate Report](#)
- [Bachelor-Level Informatics Education in Europe: Key Data & Trends, 2018/19 – 2022/23](#)
- [Minerva Informatics Equality Award Catalogue](#)
- 2025 Minerva Informatics Equality Award
 - Winner: [Sustaining Gender Diversity Over Three Decades](#) by Department of Computer Science, NTNU (NO)
 - Runner-up: [Diversifying IT – TalTech](#) by Tallinn University of Technology (EE)

- 2025 Best Dissertation Award
 - Winner: [Graph Deep Learning for Time Series Forecasting](#) by Andrea Cini, PhD graduate from the Faculty of Informatics, Università della Svizzera italiana (CH)
 - Runners-up:
 - [Sentiment in Software Engineering](#) by Nathan Cassee, TU Eindhoven (NL)
 - [Fairness Analysis of Graph Neural Networks for Behavioral User Modeling](#) by Erasmo Purificato, Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg (DE)
 - [Enhancing Fault Diagnosis in Safety-Critical Cyber-Physical Systems](#) by Drishti Yadav, TU Wien (AT)
 - Distinguished finalists:
 - [Resource Allocation and Scheduling Problems in Computing Continua for AI Applications](#) by Federica Filippini, Politecnico di Milano (IT)
 - [Deep Learning Methods for Point Matching, Visual Localization and 3D Reconstruction](#) by Shuzhe Wang, Aalto University (FI)

Data

- [2023-2024 academic year statistics and new country \(Iceland\) in the IE HE Data Portal](#)

Events

- European Informatics Leaders Summit – ECSS 2025, including 10 sessions, a welcome reception and a social activity.
The [ECSS Highlights](#) and [Closing Statements](#) summarise main discussions, while the following links provide rundown details and downloadable presentation materials for specific sessions:
 - [Leaders Workshop – How to Cope with Changes in Informatics Departments?](#)
 - [Professional Development Workshop for Early Career Researchers](#)
 - [Keynote Session – Integrating Quantum Technologies into European Informatics Departments](#)
 - [Upskilling & Societal Engagement Workshop](#), co-organised with IE member NIAs
 - [Green ICT and ICT for Green Workshop](#)
 - [Open Science & Open Source Workshop](#)
 - [D&I WG Workshop – Voices of Inclusion: Experiences and Initiatives](#)
 - [Ethics WG Workshop – Societal Impact of ICT and Its Interaction with Human Beings](#)
 - [IE Awards Ceremony](#)
 - [Informatics Europe Annual General Assembly](#)
(IE members only: login to access in “IE Members' Documents”)
- [United for Impact: Women in Informatics](#) webinar
- [ITiCSE 2025](#)
- [IE Summer School on Informatics Education Research - SCHIER 2025](#)
- [ICODSIP 2025](#)
- [Women in Digital Summit 2025](#)

Conclusion & Future Outlook

In 2025, Informatics Europe continued to translate its strategic priorities into concrete actions, strengthening its role as a trusted partner for academic institutions and a recognised voice in European discussions on Informatics education, research, and policy. The breadth of activities presented in this report reflects a coordinated effort to address both timely challenges and long-term developments shaping the discipline.

Looking ahead, Informatics Europe will further support its members in navigating a rapidly evolving landscape, marked by the increasing impact of AI, growing needs for sustainability and ethical responsibility, and shrinking national and European funds. Ongoing investment in data-driven insights, community-led initiatives, and targeted services will remain central to this effort.

At the same time, continuing to attract experts to volunteer their time and knowledge for the good of the discipline, and to enlarge the base of institutions directly supporting IE's mission, will be key to ensuring that Informatics in Europe keeps growing as a cohesive, influential and forward-looking discipline.

We encourage members to share this report within their institutions and to engage in ongoing activities supporting Informatics Europe's mission and the future of the discipline.

Annex - Organisational Structure

Board of Directors (2025)

- **Jean-Marc Jézéquel** (President) – IRISA/University of Rennes (FR)
- **Marco Aiello** (Vice President, Green ICT) – University of Stuttgart (DE)
- **Kim Mens** (Vice President, Membership) – Université catholique de Louvain (BE)
- **Elisabetta Di Nitto** (Treasurer, Ethics) – Politecnico di Milano (IT)
- **Lenuta Alboaie** (Open Science) – Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași (RO)
- **Přemek Brada** (Data Analysis & Reporting) – University of West Bohemia in Pilsen (CZ)
- **Harald Gall** (Department Evaluation) – University of Zurich (CH)
- **Gert Jervan** (Cybersecurity) – Tallinn University of Technology (EE)
- **Dimka Karastoyanova** (Early Career Researchers) – University of Groningen (NL)
- **Ernestina Menasalvas** (Up/Re-skilling) – Technical University of Madrid (ES)
- **Simona Motogna** (Diversity & Inclusion) – Babeş-Bolyai University (RO)
- **Ana C. R. Paiva** (Membership and Data Analysis & Reporting) – University of Porto (PT)
- **Heri Ramampiaro** (National Informatics Associations Relations) – NTNU (NO)
- **Jan Vahrenhold** (Education) – University of Münster (DE)
- **Enrico Nardelli** (SCHIER) – Università di Roma "Tor Vergata" (ex-officio, Past President)
- **Nuria Anguera** (IE Office; ex-officio, Executive Director)

Informatics Europe Office

- **Nuria Anguera** – Executive Director
- **Kit Wan Chui** – Communications & Admin
- **Marimar Rodriguez** – Admin & Accounting (until June)
- **Maria Eddison** – Accounting & Membership (from May)
- **Svetlana Tikhonenko** – Web, Data & Analysis

Working Groups

IE WGs bring together volunteer experts from member institutions to address strategic topics in Informatics. Each WG focuses on a specific theme, enabling coordinated knowledge exchange, the development of recommendations and best practices, and collective action that feeds into IE's broader activities and policy contributions.

The goals, ongoing activities, and participants of each WG are detailed in dedicated webpages:

- **Data Analysis and Reporting**: Enabling evidence-based decision-making with higher education Data
- **Diversity and Inclusion**: Advancing inclusive academic communities and equitable software design
- **Early Career Researchers**: Supporting the next generation of researchers within and beyond academia
- **Education Research**: Strengthening the community and advancing Informatics as a core subject across all educational levels.

- **Ethics**: Promoting ethical awareness and responsibility in Informatics research, education, and technology
- **Green ICT**: Leveraging ICT to drive sustainability across society while reducing its environmental impact
- **Open Science**: Assessing how open initiatives shape Informatics research and higher education
- **Software Research**: Positioning software as a strategic research priority in Europe
- **Policy Recommendations**: Providing coordinated responses to public consultations aligned with IE priorities (open to NIAs).

For enquiries and feedback about this report,
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